

Comments on the GHG Protocol Scope 2 Revision

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Abstract

This paper analyzes the implications of the proposed revision of the Greenhouse Gas Protocol Scope 2 Guidance for electricity-market dynamics and energy attribute certificate (EAC) markets. It focuses on three core technical dimensions: (1) hourly temporal matching and its systemic effects on power systems; (2) deliverability criteria and geographic constraints based on bidding zones; and (3) changes in EAC price formation and their consequences for corporate participation. Drawing on the power-systems literature and the International Energy Agency's six-phase framework for variable renewable energy (VRE) integration, the authors argue that both hourly temporal granularity and more spatially explicit accounting are necessary prerequisites for advancing toward power systems supplied by 100% renewable electricity, particularly in systems at advanced VRE integration stages. The analysis suggests that the revised accounting rules are likely to incentivize firms to further optimize their consumption profiles in a grid-supportive manner, strengthening demand-side management practices already observable in mature electricity and EAC markets. This trend is expected to intensify under growing national commitments to clean energy deployment, rising electricity demand, and constraints on adding new generation capacity. Hourly temporal granularity is expected to enhance incentives for demand-side flexibility and energy storage, which are critical for reducing renewable energy curtailment. Increased locational granularity, in turn, can better reflect transmission constraints, address congestion, and promote investment in optimally sited generation assets. Although the proposed revisions substantially increase complexity, including operational and transactional challenges for suppliers, traders, and end-users, these burdens can be partially alleviated by specialized EAC service providers operating on aggregation models analogous to those of energy retailers. The authors conclude that proposed changes would benefit grid decarbonization, particularly in high-VRE systems where progress might otherwise stall, and support grid-supportive demand-side management. Overall, benefits of enhanced temporal and spatial granularity in Scope 2 accounting outweigh added complexity, supported by phased implementation, exemptions for small and medium-sized enterprises, and standardized load-profile approaches. From a societal perspective, the revision supports Sustainable Development Goal 7 "Affordable and Clean Energy" by increasing renewable energy penetration and ideally improving energy service reliability through better temporal and regional matching of generation and demand.

Keywords: Greenhouse gas protocol scope 2, Energy attribute certificates, Hourly temporal matching, Locational granularity, Demand-side flexibility

1 Introduction

The Greenhouse Gas Protocol (GHG Protocol) establishes an approach for companies to measure and report their greenhouse gas emissions. Developed to bring consistency and comparability to corporate climate disclosures, it provides a methodological foundation for organizations across diverse sectors and jurisdictions.

Since its introduction in 2001, the GHG Protocol has become an influential private standard (Green 2010). It is used in disclosure initiatives, such as the Climate Disclosure Project (CDP), and is referenced within regulatory frameworks, including the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) (European Financial Reporting Advisory Group (EFRAG) 2024) and International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) Sustainability Disclosure Standards. Its widespread application is reflected in reporting practice: in 2016, 92% of Fortune 500 companies, and in 2023, 97% of disclosing S&P 500 companies reporting to CDP, used the GHG Protocol directly or indirectly through programs based on it (World Resources Institute 2025; GHG Protocol 2025a).

The current structure of the GHG Protocol is the result of successive additions that responded to evolving reporting needs. The Corporate Standard laid the foundation for corporate greenhouse gas accounting and defined direct operational emissions. The Corporate Value Chain (Scope 3) Standard, introduced in 2011, broadened the framework to include upstream and downstream value chain emissions. The Scope 2 Guidance (GHG Protocol 2025b), released in 2015, added a dedicated methodology for attributing emissions associated with purchased electricity, steam, heat and cooling. Under the Scope 2 Guidance, emissions are calculated using two complementary approaches: the location-based method, which reflects the average emissions intensity of the electricity grid where consumption occurs, and the market-based method, which reflects emissions associated with contractual instruments such as power purchase agreements (PPAs) or energy attribute certificates (EACs). EACs provide the mechanism through which consumers can substantiate claims about the use of renewable or low-carbon electricity. They are issued, traded and retired within tracking systems to ensure unique ownership of attributes. Common examples include Renewable Energy Certificates (RECs) in North America and Guarantees of Origin (GOs) in Europe. (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency 2025)

The Scope 2 Guidance is currently being revised with the purpose of improving conceptual clarity, addressing inconsistencies in application, and incorporating advances in electricity-market and certificate-system data. These refinements are intended to ensure that accounting practices remain in alignment with evolving market conditions.

As part of this revision, the Scope 2 Technical Working Group (TWG) and the Independent Standards Board (ISB) have outlined several key updates (GHG Protocol 2025c). The proposed changes focus on four central areas. First, the proposed revision would update and clarify key definitions, including the concepts of contractual instruments, market boundaries, and residual mixes. Second, it would introduce a revised hierarchy for location-based emission factors that prioritize more granular and geographically representative grid data where available. Third, for the market-based method, a shift toward hourly temporal matching is foreseen when contractual instruments are used. This would replace the annual matching approach under the current Guidance. Fourth, the document sets out new deliverability criteria which should ensure that contractual instruments represent electricity that can be physically supplied to the reporting entity. Hence, these changes would directly affect the conditions under which EACs can be

used to make market-based claims.

As such, the proposed updates have led to differing interpretations within and beyond the Scope 2 TWG. Several organizations, including companies such as Meta, General Motors, and Microsoft, have expressed support for similar reforms in earlier joint statements (*Greenhouse Gas Protocol Scope 2 Guidance Modernization 2023*). However, other actors raised concerns about the practicality and potential market impacts of the proposed requirements, particularly the move toward hourly matching and the adoption of more restrictive deliverability criteria (Center for Resource Solutions 2025; American Council on Renewable Energy (ACORE) 2025; Emissions First 2025). According to these stakeholders, such adjustments do not correspond to current market structures, could create substantial administrative burdens, and may ultimately limit participation in certificate markets (Mowinckel and Clausen 2025). A subgroup of nine TWG members voiced similar reservations, favoring the continuation of annual matching and broader geographic boundaries as the standard approach, while viewing more granular methods as an optional refinement rather than a default expectation (9 Members of the Scope 2 Technical Working Group 2025).

Given these differing perspectives, this paper examines a set of technical questions that are central to understanding how the proposed Scope 2 revisions may affect electricity-market interactions and, in particular, the functioning of EAC markets. The analysis focuses on three themes that reflect the main points of contention in the current debate:

- Hourly matching: the feasibility of introducing hourly granularity and its potential effects on electricity systems and EAC markets.
- Deliverability and bidding-zone boundaries: whether the proposed geographic restrictions for contractual instruments align with physical system conditions and support renewable deployment.
- Willingness to pay: how changes in EAC pricing may affect corporate participation in voluntary procurement and the functioning of EAC markets.

The objective of this paper is to assess these questions through a structured synthesis of consultation documents, stakeholder submissions, and relevant literature from power-system analysis and energy economics. By integrating these insights, the study develops a technically informed perspective on selected points of debate and clarifies how the proposed Scope 2 design choices may interact with system behavior, procurement practices, and EAC-market dynamics.

2 Background

Key aspects of the market from related literature are condensed into a groundwork for illustration of the effects of the proposed changes.

2.1 System stability and emission reduction

The electricity grid is in stable operation at a frequency of 50 Hz or 60 Hz, depending on the country, as long as the total energy produced is consumed at the same time. In this context, *system adequacy* describes the ability of the generators in the power system to supply the total energy demand at all times. This fundamental relationship directly influences pos-

sible measures to reduce green house gas emissions: A reduction of emissions can only be achieved through an increase in actually produced and absorbed variable renewable energy sources (VRE) $E_{\text{actually produced}}$ as portion of all VRE available $E_{\text{available}}$:

Figure 1: System emissions are reduced if $E_{\text{actually produced}}$ increases

- $E_{\text{actually produced}}$: Energy from VRE absorbed by the system
- $E_{\text{available}}$: VRE energy potential (weather dependent)
- E_{fossil} : Fossil-fuel based energy absorbed by the system
- E_{demand} : Energy demand in the whole system
- E_{excess} : Curtailed energy from VRE

An increase in $E_{\text{actually produced}}$ and therefore a reduction in overall system emissions can be achieved in two ways, either by increasing $E_{\text{available}}$ (installing more generation capacity from VRE) or by decreasing E_{excess} (reducing curtailment of energy from VRE). Note that all energy quantities in Figure 1 change over time and the sankey chart depicts a snapshot at one point in time. E_{excess} and E_{fossil} both can be larger than zero at the same time, if the electricity grid cannot transport all $E_{\text{available}}$ to the places where it is needed.

In a system with a low share of renewable generation, additionally installed VRE production capacity increases $E_{\text{available}}$ and lowers overall system emissions, because the available energy produced by a new, carbon-free generator, is fully absorbed by the grid and replaces the same amount of energy from fossil-fuel-based generators ($E_{\text{excess}} = 0$ in this case). If new VRE production capacity is installed and still $E_{\text{excess}} = 0$ at all times, the marginal emission reduction of additional VRE production capacity stays constant.

At some level of VRE integration, $E_{\text{available}}$ will exceed the demand during some hours, e.g. on a sunny holiday at noon, yielding $E_{\text{excess}} > 0$. Transport capacity limitations of the transmission grid between $E_{\text{available}}$ and E_{demand} could further increase E_{excess} and therefore decrease $E_{\text{actually produced}}$. The marginal emission reduction of added VRE generation capacity decreases significantly without further measures, as $E_{\text{actually produced}}$ does not increase at the same speed as $E_{\text{available}}$ anymore. At this point, the variable generation from carbon-free resources significantly influences the system operation, making it a system with a high share of renewable generation. If E_{demand} could be shifted to the hours with $E_{\text{excess}} > 0$ in such system, the marginal emission reduction of added VRE production capacity would remain constant. The following measures could help reducing E_{excess} in a system with high VRE integration:

1. Storage could absorb E_{excess} and supply consumers later during hours with lower $E_{\text{available}}$
2. Consumers could shift their consumption in time (E_{demand} becomes flexible)
3. Local proximity of VRE generation and demand reduces transmission grid congestions

This represents a paradigm shift in the power system: The consumers have to plan their consumption along the availability of energy from VRE in dimensions of time and location. To introduce flexible demand and storage systems at the optimal places in the system in a meaningful order of magnitude, significant investments and adjustments of industry processes are necessary. Although most of the enabling technology is already commercially available today, regulatory frameworks and economic incentives are needed to motivate stakeholders to tackle technical and operational challenges.

2.2 Phases of VRE integration in existing systems

In their study „Integrating Solar and Wind”, the Renewable Integration and Secure Electricity Unit of the International Energy Agency (IEA) defines six phases of VRE integration (Kuwahata, Jorquera Copier, and Hevia-Koch 2024) depicted in figure 2.

IEA. CC BY 4.0.

Figure 2: Phases of variable renewable integration, 2023-2030, taken from page 12 in (Kuwahata, Jorquera Copier, and Hevia-Koch 2024)

The low phases (1-3) and high phases (4-6) are similar to the aforementioned phases of low and high share of VRE in the previous section 2.1, where we describe the relevant measures for emission reduction in the respective phases. Today’s power systems and near future projections are then set in relation to the six phases in figure 3.

The authors expect even more countries to reach phases of high VRE integration until 2030.

Figure 3: Selected countries in phases of variable renewable integration, 2023-2030, taken from page 28 in (Kuwahata, Jorquera Copier, and Hevia-Koch 2024)

In the latest „IEA Renewables 2025 analysis and forecast” they expect renewable electricity additions until 2030 in the scale of today’s combined installed power generation capacity of China, the EU and Japan (Abdelilah et al. 2025). The emission reduction measures for systems with high VRE integration are relevant today, and will become even more relevant over the next years. In (Holttinen et al. 2021) the status of VRE integration around the world is assessed and the need for flexibility is explained. System flexibility, and more specific demand side flexibility and storage have been identified as key issues of a power system with high integration of VRE among other studies in (RDIC of ENTSO-E 2024), (Chernyakhovskiy and Streitmatter 2024), (Cochran et al. 2021) and (Heard et al. 2017). Beyond that, the relation between tailored economic incentives and regulatory frameworks on the development of flexibility is named a key driver of available demand flexibility (Massaoudi, Davis, and Akramul Haque 2025). In (Liu et al. 2022) the authors recommend to introduce market-based incentives for demand side flexibility to shift towards off-peak load hours. The authors of (Cruz et al. 2020) state that demand side flexibility can become responsive to system requirements and to a certain extent compensate the stochastic behavior of RECs in the absence of proper energy storage media, if appropriate incentives are given.

3 Analysis

Building on the groundwork provided above, we address the specific aspects of hourly matching, deliverability and bidding-zone boundaries, and willingness-to-pay. Furthermore, we touch on the overarching issue of complexity increase for market participants.

3.1 Hourly granularity

In the previous sections, the current status and near-future trends for the integration of VRE into the energy system were presented. From literature from different fields of the power systems community we conclude that demand side flexibility and storage systems are essential for the energy transition towards a fully renewable energy system. Such an energy system would conform to the goal of zero emission energy production and therefore contribute to achieving the climate goals for the power sector, which is the declared goal of the GHG Protocol.

The annual granularity of the GHG Protocol, as it is today, sets incentives for energy producers to produce from renewable sources instead of fossil fuels by recognizing the total amount of annual produced carbon-free energy (CFE). This incentive is suitable for systems in low VRE integration phases. Systems in high VRE integration phases require incentives that encourage consumers to make their demand flexible or even to invest in on-site storage, to minimize E_{excess} . Hourly granular CFE implement exactly such recommended incentives, as they motivate energy consumers to adjust their consumption to the available renewable energy that changes over time, $E_{\text{available}}$. The „Renewables 2025” IEA report (Abdelilah et al. 2025) states that many countries are already today in a phase of high VRE integration, consequently the emission reduction measures for high VRE integration systems presented in the previous section become relevant today. Hourly granular carbon emission accounting would offer additional incentives which could accelerate the needed paradigm shift. The authors of (Ballentine and Falwell 2025) also suggest introducing a granular (hourly and spatially aligned) residual mix factor to accurately track the emissions (Ballentine and Falwell 2025).

3.2 Local granularity

If large amounts of VRE-generated energy are transmitted through the grid, the operating limits of transmission lines can be reached during peak hours. This leads to immediate curtailment of VRE and adjustment of grid operation, which generates high costs for system operators that are ultimately passed on to all stakeholders. Curtailment also reduces the actually produced VRE output $E_{\text{actually produced}}$ and therefore lowers the share of carbon-free energy generation. A prominent example of this phenomenon is the time-varying congestion in the northern German transmission grid that leads to the curtailment of off-shore windparks (Frysztacki and Brown 2020). Congestion in the transmission grid can be mitigated through costly and time-intensive grid reinforcement measures, such as HVDC projects ”SuedLink” and ”SuedOstLink” in Germany. They are designed to transport electricity from off-shore wind parks in the north to consumption centers in the south. If more production capacity were built closer to consumption centers, less reinforcement and more efficient grid operation would become possible (Sofia and Dvorkin 2025). CFE that can only be traded within the local boundaries of the grid sets incentives to invest in VRE production closer to consumption.

This effect also exists between electricity markets and their (often national) grids. In today’s GHG Protocol definitions, very large grids are defined in which EACs can be traded independent of their physical possibility to reach the intended recipient. For example, most of Europe is defined as one grid, which could result in recognizing large amounts of wind energy produced in Norway for electricity consumption taking place in Southern Germany (an increase to the aforementioned intra-grid congestion). To better reflect these limits of transmission between grids and to align the concept of EAC with the electricity market boundaries and grid operations, a higher local granularity with stricter geographic matching is required. Accounting for CFE created somewhere where it can physically not be delivered to the consumer is attributionally incorrect, and, with higher VRE integration levels, would not result in higher $E_{\text{actually produced}}$. Note, that the power or EAC provided by a certain generator does not flow to the consumer which procured that power or EAC, but instead the power is merely added to the grid and taken out elsewhere. Direct traceability between generation and consumption is not possible. Nevertheless, granular location accounting is needed to incentivize building generation which does not lead to grid congestion. Otherwise the generation would need to be curtailed by the grid operator.

On the other hand, countries with lower VRE integration levels might not be on a practical maturity level nor face a physical congestion need to incentivize such granular deployment of VRE generation. Furthermore, managing a large number of regional zones when procuring EACs might result in extremely increased complexity for a multinational company. We will discuss these aspects in the following section.

3.3 Complexity

Operational Complexity

A potential barrier to the implementation and actual effectiveness of the revised standard to reduce GHG emissions is the additional operational complexity. This added complexity affects both the companies that buy the certificates, the generators that produce the certificates, and the companies that trade the certificates. Among the factors that contribute to a high level of complexity and additional cost are

- higher transaction costs,
- detailed load and generation data,
- specialized IT systems,
- Know how & human resources,
- more complex contracts (additional legal capacity required on all sides), and
- especially challenging demand side management for companies with small procurement teams.

We present the challenges to the supplier side and trading side, and the buyer side, and analyze a key role trading companies can play in overcoming this complexity.

Supplier and trading side: Électricité de France (EDF) emphasizes that granular matching requires detailed consumption data, collaboration with customers, and sophisticated optimization of portfolios to meet specified hourly CFE levels, supported by dedicated IT systems and specialist service providers. Suppliers must handle time-stamped certificates, potentially sub-hourly settlement, and more complex contract structures (e.g. hybrid PPAs with storage), which raise transaction costs and legal workload on both buyer and seller side. NESO/AFRY's analysis of 24/7 CFE trading similarly finds that suppliers and traders must invest in new data platforms, forecasting tools, and optimization models to manage 24/7 CFE positions alongside energy and balancing markets. These studies suggest that the incremental complexity and cost are manageable for large, sophisticated utilities with diversified portfolios, but are likely to be significant for smaller suppliers and for actors in less mature registries or markets. (NESO 2025; EDF 2025)

Buyer side: For large corporate consumers, hourly matching and tighter geographic rules involve managing high-resolution load data across many sites, investing in new software, and redesigning procurement and risk strategies away from a small set of annual-matched PPAs toward more dynamic portfolio management and demand-side management. (NESO 2025; EDF 2025)

Reducing the complexity

A solution to the added complexity of procuring EACs with hourly and location granular reporting can be a setup similar to how most companies procure their energy: Instead of buying the energy at the power market themselves, they rely on energy providers that aggregate many consumers, forecast their joint consumption, and buy the necessary energy for each point in time (usually these are 15 minute windows). Given the large number of consumers that they aggregate, the energy providers can predict the needed amount of energy with high accuracy. If companies were to purchase their EACs through a similar setup, they would not face the increased complexity of hourly and location granular accounting. This complexity would be handled by the specialized company, which, similar to the case with energy, would profit from scaling effects and aggregating a large number of consumers that want to buy EACs. What would remain to do for a company that wants to purchase EACs for their electricity consumption is to report the consumption that they had and the specialized company provides the EACs for that consumption. Given that the role, setup, and tasks of such a specialized EAC-providing company are similar if not even identical to that of an energy provider, operating such a company is feasible and well within reach. Possibly, such a setup could even reduce the complexity of procuring EACs for the individual consumer.

3.4 Willingness to pay

Several studies on the development of EACs prices in hourly matching schemes indicate moderate price premiums up to a certain coverage level, beyond which a sharp price increase is expected. Estimates of this “critical” matching level range from 75% in system-operation modeling for Great Britain to roughly 98% (NESO 2025) in European system-level studies (Riepin and Brown 2024). The French supplier EDF finds a 100% hourly-matched PPA to be around 40% more expensive compared to an annual-matched PPA (EDF 2025) with a steep cost increase at a coverage of around 95%. This implies that pushing hourly coverage to 100%, as net-zero Scope 2 targets would effectively require, comes at a significantly higher, though still uncertain, cost. Consequently, concerns have been raised that mandating very high hourly matching and deliverability criteria could have the unintended effect of companies scaling back participation in voluntary markets or disengaging from renewable electricity procurement altogether (9 Members of the Scope 2 Technical Working Group 2025). This chapter therefore examines how sensitive voluntary demand is to rising prices and whether evidence on businesses’ willingness to pay for certificate premiums allows for conclusions on the revised Scope 2 Guidance’s effects.

Studies and market analyses show that companies’ willingness to pay for green electricity in voluntary markets is generally positive but limited and price-sensitive. Large buyers are prepared to pay a premium for credible renewable products (PPAs, green tariffs, certificates, etc.) where these support climate targets and hedging of risks (Martinsen and Mouilleron 2020). However, most businesses face budget constraints and seek prices close to standard utility tariffs (NREL 2020). For example, the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) found in a comprehensive analysis of corporate sourcing of renewable electricity, covering data from 2400 large companies in more than 40 countries, that the rapid growth of corporate sourcing has been driven mainly by arrangements that are close to cost parity with conventional power, noting that economic and financial drivers are among the top three reasons for companies to procure green electricity (IRENA 2018). Similarly, a recent review of studies on the demand elasticity for voluntary procurement of EACs in US markets concludes that higher prices of

EACs would reduce the amount of clean energy procured (E3 2024). Based on the reviewed studies, the authors model a two-fold and four-fold increase of the base price (3.7 USD/MWh) at - 15% and -100% demand elasticity (E3 2024). Other reviewed studies here focus on residential consumers (Herbes et al. 2020), do not differentiate between residential and business consumers (Mewton and Cacho 2011) or exclude elasticity and willingness to pay aspects in their modeling (Wimmers and Madlener 2023), limiting its direct applicability to corporate Scope 2 questions.

In conclusion, empirical evidence regarding firms' willingness to pay for green power certificates remains limited. The available studies provide only indicative ranges and primarily rely on scenario modeling rather than on observed behavioral responses. Consequently, both the magnitude and the statistical significance of potential demand reductions in response to price increases remain uncertain. Similarly, the future trajectory of corporate willingness to pay is largely unknown, particularly as the 2030 net-zero targets for Scope 1 and 2 emissions, adopted by many large multinational enterprises, draw closer.

The literature reviewed to date primarily examines large multinational purchasers operating in relatively mature markets, such as the United States and the United Kingdom, where advanced procurement capabilities and regulatory frameworks already favor renewable electricity sourcing. Within this segment, demand for green power attributes appears to exhibit price sensitivity. At the same time, these actors are among the principal proponents of more granular temporal (e.g., hourly) and locational matching schemes for renewable electricity attributes.

4 Statement on the Alternative Position

Nine members of the technical working group, who worked on the revision of the GHG Protocol Scope 2, have issued a response (9 Members of the Scope 2 Technical Working Group 2025) to the proposed changes to the GHG protocol scope 2, because they have a different opinion than the rest of the technical working group. These nine members raise technical and feasibility concerns in their response. For each of these concerns, we have concluded the following view from the reviewed literature above.

4.1 Technical concerns

Argument 1: Research has shown that hourly matching does not improve scientific validity due to intra-regional transmission congestion.

Our opinion Hourly matching improves the steering effect of the GHG Protocol Scope 2 towards an electric power grid consisting of 100% renewable generation. To further improve the steering effect, also more granular location accounting is needed to counteract intra-regional transmission congestion. Therefore, intra-regional transmission congestion is not an argument against hourly matching but for location granular accounting.

Argument 2: Research has shown that hourly matching does not improve scientific validity due to [...] double-counting inaccuracies.

Our opinion Double-counting is addressed by the proposed revision of the GHG Protocol Scope 2 and tangible solutions of accounting that prohibit double-counting exist. We therefore do not agree that double-counting is a road block towards hourly matching.

Arguments 3, 4, and 5: Research has shown that hourly matching does not improve scientific validity due to [...] the potential to inadvertently slow system-wide decarbonization progress. The Technical Working Group Discussion Topic Overview omits key research from groups like the International Energy Agency or Rocky Mountain institute showing that in many contexts, stricter temporal and geographic matching can lead to lower climate impact than more conventional sourcing strategies.

Our opinion It is correct that hourly matching and more granular location accounting can lead to projects being realized that have a smaller carbon emission reduction than projects that would be realized under the old reporting rules. The difference, however, is small and, once a high share of energy production in an electric grid is renewable, it is crucial to build generation and storage that facilitates the full de-carbonization of the grid. These are not necessarily projects with the largest annual production but with the bigger impact towards a fully carbon-free electric energy grid.

4.2 Feasibility concerns

Argument 1: Operational complexity Most companies - especially those with globally distributed operations, where energy needs can range from a few kilowatts to multiple megawatts across thousands of locations - would lack the resources to manage added data needs, reporting requirements, auditing procedures, and contracting complexity.

Our opinion While procuring hourly and within narrower location boundaries is a lot more challenging, EACs providing companies can help keep the operational complexity limited.

Argument 2: Market constraints Even in parts of the U.S., such as the Southeast, buyers report that procurement remains effectively impossible after years of effort, with projects priced out of reach and on-site renewables already maxed out. In such cases, narrowing geographic boundaries further would remove the only remaining path to meeting emission reduction goals – driving some companies to abandon their targets altogether.

Our opinion If EACs are scarce in certain markets, then financial incentives are needed that make renewable generation price competitive. This is exactly what the proposed revision does by introducing more location granular accounting. The stated example from the US is a large pro argument for location granular accounting not an argument against it.

Argument 3a: Increased costs Hourly matching and stricter boundaries increase costs and complexity, especially for resource-constrained businesses, for whom energy is not their core business, and are procuring clean energy voluntarily.

Argument 3b: Opportunity costs Companies have highlighted the added time and expense of implementing robust software systems to support granular matching and reporting. This means that a larger share of clean energy budgets would shift toward data management instead of funding new clean energy projects to drive the impact of emission reduction.

Our opinion There are two different reasons for potential cost increases of EACs under the proposed changes: 1) added system complexity and 2) the scarcity of EACs at certain

times or in certain areas.

- About the added system complexity: If companies were to procure hourly and location granular EACs themselves, then costs would increase sharply. However, as argued previously, specialized EAC providers can shield them from this complexity. The increased complexity of the proposed changes would therefore only affect a few specialized companies, which would not lead to large cost increases of EACs. Shifting a company's consumption to times with lower costs of EACs also adds complexity. However, companies will have to add this level of complexity to their operation anyway to react to dynamic energy prices.
- About the unavailability of EACs: If prices increase because EACs are scarce at certain times or in certain areas, then these are steering signals that are needed and introduced in the GHG protocol scope revision with the purpose of steering the electric power system to 100% renewable generation.

Argument 4: Risk of disengagement Many buyers have indicated that these requirements would be extremely difficult to meet, potentially leading them to exit the voluntary market or stop using the GHG Protocol altogether. There is also a significant risk of losing – or failing to attract – small and medium enterprises (SMEs) that are still building their GHG accounting capabilities.

Our opinion EACs providers can protect companies purchasing EACs from added complexity. Furthermore, the exemptions for companies with smaller energy consumptions and the possibility to use generic load profiles or a flat load profile keep the complexity limited.

5 Conclusion

Having analyzed the literature and the proposed revision of the GHG Protocol Scope 2, we conclude that hourly matching and more granular location accounting are needed to move towards an electric power system that is 100% renewable. At the same time, we recognize that this will likely make creating EACs and procuring EACs more complex. However, we do not think the added complexity will affect companies to a large extent in withdrawing from the use of renewable energy and EACs. This is because of several reasons and possible countermeasures as follows.

Time frame Phase-In of the new regulation is planned to take several years after publication of the standard, with additional legacy clauses for existing PPAs and EAC contracts. Given that this time frame will be long enough for both producers and consumers to adapt, we assume market constraints and system complexity to be addressed and at least partly resolved due to increased market attractiveness. Where this is not the case, the exemptions and practicality considerations below would apply.

Grid Maturity Electric power grids in most western countries have already reached a share of renewable generation at which hourly matching and local granular accounting is needed. Many other countries will have reached this grid maturity by 2030, which aligns with when the revision of the GHG protocol scope 2 will come into effect.

Outsourcing Already today, companies of all sizes and differing geographical representation

can rely on a multitude of service providers for procuring and managing EACs. In a changing market, especially with the proposed long transition time frame, these providers will adopt new processes and databases to reflect the needs for more granular (hourly) and geographical management. Forecasting and hedging combined volumes will counter price fluctuations, as it is already the case today with specialized electricity trading companies.

Net Zero Targets With companies having set net zero targets e.g. with the Science-based Targets initiative (SBTi), and many of these reaching their target date in 2030 and 2035, large progressive companies will continue to reduce their carbon footprint in Scope 1 by electrifying combustion and fleets, and consequently rely on EAC for purchasing CFE for the portion of electricity they cannot decarbonize on their own, e.g. by installing PV and battery systems.

Exemptions For small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) and for companies below a certain threshold, exemptions have been defined to allow for monthly or annual matching of EAC. These companies could therefore uphold their emission reductions and continue to play a vital role in the market, especially with regards to being a supplier for large companies. Requests from large companies as part of their Scope 3 to be net zero could still be matched.

Practicality Subsequent to grid maturity and exemptions for companies based on their size and consumption, the technical unavailability of hourly granularity then allows for use of monthly or annual EAC. Use of standard load profiles for reporting purposes will be an extra effort, but appears doable in the context of GHG Protocol users being motivated to play a role in climate protection.

At the same time, proposed changes of the GHG Protocol Scope 2 would be beneficial to the decarbonization of the electric power grids globally, especially those on higher phases of VRE integration where this might otherwise stall. We also see an effect on companies to further optimize their energy consumption towards grid-supportive demand-side management - a development already seen in mature markets today and expected to further increase with countries' own commitments for clean energy, increasing electricity demand and limits to addition of generation capacity. Overall, the benefits of hourly matching and more granular location accounting out value the added complexity and potential disengagement of companies due to higher prices. From a societal perspective, the change will support the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 7 „Affordable and Clean Energy” by further increasing the share of renewable energy in the global energy mix through VRE increases and by making energy services more reliable through better regional and timely matching of generation and demand.

Declaration of competing interest

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